

Chemistry of Cyclonadienes*

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IN a nine-membered carbocyclic system, the two double bonds can take 1,2- or 1,3- or 1,4- or 1,5-positions (Scheme 1). The chemistry of 1,2-cyclonadiene (*1*)† has attracted the attention of organic chemists recently owing to the presence of two orthogonal π bonds incorporated in an isolable least carbon containing cyclic system. The allenic system, which consists of two sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms and one sp -hybridized carbon atom (Scheme 1), exhibits a combination of olefinic and acetylenic character. The stereochemistry of allene is another interesting feature in this unusual unsaturated system. The known conjugated dienes have *cis*, *cis*-(2) and *trans*-configuration (3) in *cisoid* form. Because of the required geometry of these double bonds one would anticipate certain amount of strain

in these molecules, and this might give rise to some interesting properties. The unconjugated dienes (4 and 5) are of conformational interest.

They exhibit unique physical and chemical properties which are different from common rings (5-7) and large rings (11 and above). One such unique feature of the medium-ring geometry is the existence of a certain conformation in which the opposite sides of the ring come in close proximity with each other. This can give rise to electronic interactions, and transannular reactions which involve the formation of a bond between atoms on opposite sides. The pioneer workers in this field are late Professor A. C. Cope and his associates in the U.S.A. who have done a thorough work on the eight-membered ring, and Professor V. Prelog and his coworkers in Switzerland who have worked on the ten-membered system. As part of our research programme at Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, we have been interested in the chemistry of the medium-ring dienes, cyclonadienes for the past six years. We hope that our work and others in this field has uncovered some of the chemistry which shows the resemblance and differences as compared to 8- or 10-membered system. The present lecture in memory of late Professor Basudev Banerjee for the year 1973 will devote itself to review the chemistry of cyclonadienes to-date.

Scheme 1

Synthesis of Cyclonadienes

The cyclic allene, 1,2-cyclonadiene (*1*) can be synthesized conveniently in two-step sequence¹⁻² which involves addition of dibromocarbene to the readily available *cis*-cyclo-octene (7) followed by treatment of the resulting 9,9-dibromo-bicyclo (6.1.0) nonane (8) with methyllithium (Scheme 2).

The asymmetric synthesis of optically active 1,2-cyclonadiene (*1*) has been achieved starting from

Scheme 2

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† Underlined numerals in figures are italicised in the text.

optically active *trans*-cyclooctene (9). The *trans* cyclooctene (9) is asymmetric and has been resolved into the active enantiomorphs (9A) and (9B). Rotation

Scheme 3

of the ethylenic group through the inside of the ring would result in interconversion and racemization, but this is not possible because it would require excessive steric and angle strain. The resolving agent used is the coordination complex, ethylene-(+)- α -phenyl-ethylaminedichloroplatinum. Treatment of optically active *trans*-cyclooctene (9) with bromoform and potassium *t*-butoxide gives the optically active dibromide (10) which upon treatment with methyllithium affords the optically active 1,2-cyclononadiene (1). An examination of the molecular model of *trans*-cyclooctene (9) suggests that the methylene chain screens one side of the double bond. As a result the optical purity of 10 should be as high as the olefin employed. As the reaction of 10 with methyllithium is stereospecific and the allene (1) formed is optically pure.

Scheme 4

The *cis, cis*-1,3-cyclononadiene (2) and *cis, trans*-1,3-cyclononadiene (3) are made starting from *cis*-cyclononene (11) (Scheme 4). N-Bromosuccinimide reaction gives 3-bromocyclononene (12). Dehydrobromination of 12 by potassium *t*-butoxide in DMSO for 5 minutes at room temperature gives *cis, cis*-1,3-cyclononadiene (2) in good yield⁴. On the other hand the reaction of 12 with dimethylamine yields trialkylamine (13). The amine (13) is converted to tetraalkylammonium iodide (14) by reacting with methyl iodide. The tetraalkylammonium iodide (14) on treatment with aqueous silver oxide followed by heating undergoes Hoffman elimination to give predominantly *cis, trans*-1,3-cyclononadiene (3).⁵

A convenient method of synthesis of *cis, cis*-1,4-cyclononadiene (4) has been devised by Winstein and his coworkers.⁶ This involves pyrolysis of bicyclo (6.1.0) non-2-ene (15) at 150°–170°. The isomerization reaction involves interesting homo(1,5)-sigmatropic hydrogen shift (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

Our varied interest in the chemistry of *cis, cis*-1,5-cyclononadiene (5) prompted us to search for a convenient synthesis of this diene. Our synthesis⁷ involves the treatment of a four-fold excess of readily available *cis, cis*-1,5-cyclooctadiene (16) with 1 equivalent of carbon tetrabromide and 2 equivalents

of methyl lithium in ether at -65° to get 1,2,6-cyclonatriene (17). The sodium-ammonia reduction of the triene (17) provides 6 in good yield (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

The assignment of the configurations of the double bonds and the structure of the diene (6) have been established by physical and chemical data. The molecular model construction of *cis, cis*- and *cis, trans*-isomers suggests that the latter is more strained than the former. Probably this may be one of the reasons for the stereochemical course of the sodium-ammonia reduction of the triene (17).

Even the *cis, trans*-1,5-cyclonadiene (6) has been synthesized starting from 1,2,6-cyclononatriene (17)⁸ via the unsaturated ketone (19) using the same sequence of reactions used in the synthesis of *cis, trans*-1,3-cyclonadiene (3), (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Reactions of 1,2-Cyclononadiene (1)

(1) Addition Reactions

The allenic bond incorporated in a cyclic system creates several possible modes of addition of an attacking reagent. An unsymmetrical reagent EN clearly has the option of placing either E or N at the central carbon with N or E at the terminal carbon to give products which could give rise to *cis* and *trans* as shown in Scheme 8.

Let us consider the possible reaction intermediates in the addition of an electrophilic reagent E^+-N^- to an allenic bond. Attachment of the electrophile E^+ to a terminal carbon indicates that intermediate

Scheme 8

vinyl cation 19 is probably formed. Alternatively, attachment of E^+ at the central carbon indicates that allylic cation 21 may be formed. Furthermore, selectivity between the terminal and central carbons can be taken as a measure of the relative stabilities of vinylic and allylic ions 19 and 21. However, it is important to note that the allylic ion (21) formed as the result of central attack is probably non-planar and does not resemble a resonance stabilized allylic cation 22. The terminal 2p orbital of 21 is orthogonal to the π -bonding orbitals, and electron delocalization is, therefore, at a minimum. The stability of 21 is probably close to that of an alkyl cation, and to achieve allylic resonance stabilization, the ion must rotate 90° about the σ bond to form 22. The alternative form of non-planar ion 21 is the bridged ion 20 in which locus of initial attack has lost some of its meaning. Bridged ion of this type is invoked to explain the frequent occurrence of stereospecific *trans* addition of halogens to alkenes. However, the precise description of the bonding in bridged ion 20 still remains obscure (Scheme 9).⁹

The question of interest as regards central attack of the electrophile is whether, in the course of the reaction, the resonance stabilized allylic intermediate 22 does indeed intervene, or whether the products

Scheme 9

are derived largely or entirely from non-planar allylic intermediates related to 20 or 21. Evidence as to the nature of the intermediates involved in addition reaction can in principle be obtained from studies employing optically active allenes. Thus, if planar allylic intermediate similar to 22 is formed to any important extent from a dissymmetric allene prior to the product-forming steps, the product is expected

to be racemic. If, however, the initially formed non-planar intermediate **20** or **21** reacts to form product faster than it could interconvert to planar intermediate **22**, optically active product could result.

(a) *Addition of Bromine*:¹⁰⁻¹¹ Bromine addition can usually be arrested at the monoadduct stage, and the orientation corresponds to central electrophilic attack and terminal nucleophilic attack. Bromination of 1,2-cyclononadiene (**1**) in methanol gives a mixture of *cis* bromoethers **23** and **24** with **24** as the major product. Models indicate that the approach of an electrophilic reagent from within the ring is more hindered than from without (Scheme 10). Formation of **24** can be explained as the result of a transannular hydride shift occurring in the allylic cation intermediate formed by electrophilic attack of

Scheme 10

bromine at the central allenic carbon. The nature of the allylic intermediate is not known.

(b) *Hydrogen Halide*¹²⁻¹³: There are several problems connected with the addition of hydrogen halide to allenes. For example, the rearrangement of the starting allene and rearrangement of the initial products can severely complicate the reaction picture, and in HBr addition, it is difficult to completely suppress corresponding radical addition reactions. Because of these difficulties, it is difficult to evaluate the experimental results reported in the literature. However, the addition of HCl or HBr to 1,2-cyclononadiene gives only 3-chlorocyclononene or 3-bromocyclononene (**25**), Scheme 11. This is indicative of allylic intermediate formed by central protonation. The possibility of the isomerization of the

Scheme 11

allene to conjugated diene prior to addition has not been excluded.

(c) *Water*^{12,14}: Hydration reactions of allenes are difficult to evaluate. Several of these reactions utilize mercuric salts and strong acids as catalysts. In the presence of mercuric salt the reaction probably involves initial oxymercuration followed by demercuration. However, the reaction of **1** with water either in the presence of mercuric salt or acid gives only 3-hydroxycyclononene (**26**) as shown in Scheme 12.

Scheme 12

(d) *Oxymercuration*¹⁵⁻¹⁷: In contrast to hydration and hydrogen halide addition, oxymercuration of allenes is remarkably well behaved. Rearrangement of the starting allene is not observed, and the adducts do not rearrange to more stable products under the reaction conditions. The adducts are therefore, formed under kinetic control, and their structures are indicative of the effect of substitution on the orientation of addition. The reaction of **1** with HgCl_2 in ethanol gives 2-chloromercuric-3-ethoxycyclononene (**27**), Scheme 13. The configuration has been established as *cis* based on $\text{Hg}^{199}\text{-H}^1$ spin-spin coupling. The oxymercuration of optically active 1,2-cyclononadiene strongly suggests that the stereospecificity of oxymercuration is dependent on the nature of the mercuric electrophile. The highest level of activity retained in the allylic ether (**28**) formed by protodemercuration of the initial product **27**, and the lowest on the addition of mercuric chloride. In general, the higher the electronegativity of the ligand X in the electrophile HgX^+ , the lower is the observed stereospecificity.

We have illustrated the synthetic utility of oxymercuration-demercuration of cyclic allenes in the

Scheme 13

synthesis of α, β -unsaturated ketones in two steps. The first step involves the oxymercuration reaction combined with the reduction of the oxymercureal intermediate by sodium borohydride *in situ* according to the procedure of Brown and coworkers. The method provides a convenient method of hydrating cyclic allenes in a regioselective manner. The second step in the synthesis involves mild oxidation of 3-hydroxycyclononene (26) with activated manganese dioxide to α, β -unsaturated ketone (29) in good yield, Scheme 14.

(f) *Chlorosulphonyl Isocyanate*²⁰: Chlorosulphonyl isocyanate (ClSO_2NCO) is evidently an electrophilic reagent that adds to 1. by a two-step dipolar cycloaddition reaction to form β -lactam (33). The product may be considered formed by initial electrophilic attack of the reagent at the central allenic carbon to give a dipolar intermediate (32) which may cyclize to 33 (Scheme 16).

(g) *Ketene*²¹⁻²²: Dimethylketene adds to 1 in a regioselective manner to form the bicyclic α, β -

Scheme 14

(e) *Sulphenyl Chloride*¹⁸⁻¹⁹: The addition of 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride to 1,2-cyclononadiene (1) is reported to orient the sulphenyl group to the central allenic carbon and the chloride to a terminal position in the product (31). Jacobs and coworkers have suggested that the reaction takes place *via* episulphonium ion (30) as shown in Scheme 15.

Scheme 16

Scheme 15

unsaturated ketone (34), Scheme 17. This reaction has been utilized very recently in the synthesis of isocaryophyllene (35).

(h) *Hydroboration*²³⁻²⁶: Hydroboration of 1,2-cyclononadiene (1) with diborane followed by alkaline hydrogen peroxide oxidation gives mainly cyclononane (35). The study involving diborane is difficult to interpret partly because of the complications

Scheme 17

that arise in the oxidation step, and partly because addition proceeds through monoalkyl-, dialkyl- and trialkyl stages each with different steric and electronic requirements. One investigation that avoids these complications involves the hydroboration of the allene with monofunctional borane, disiamylborane or 4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3-dioxo-2-borinane (TDB). The addition of TDB to *1* gives products corresponding to 100% attack of boron on the central carbon atom. It has been shown by NMR that the product contains 85% of *cis*-isomer (*37*) and 15% of *trans*-isomer (*38*). Assuming that hydroboration involves a four-center transition state (Scheme 18), the selectivity of the allene could be solely dictated by the steric congestion in the transition state.

Scheme 18

1,2-Cyclononadiene (*1*) on dihydroboration-oxidation gives 0.6% *trans*-cyclononene (*39*), 0.3% cyclononanone (*35*), 31% cyclononanol (*40*), 22% 1,2-cyclononane diol (*41*) and 0.8% 1,3-cyclononane diol (*42*), Scheme 19. The formation of these products can be explained via 1,1- or 1,2- or 1,3-diorganoborane intermediate.

Scheme 20

(i) *Benzynes*²⁷: The reaction of benzyne with 1,2-cyclononadiene (*1*) proceeds to give a small amount of (2+2) addition product (**43**) and mainly the hydrogen abstraction product leading to the formation of 1,3-diene (**44**), Scheme 20.²⁰

Scheme 19

(j) *Carbene*²⁸: The treatment of 1,2-cyclononadiene (*1*) with one equivalent of phenyl-(tribromomethyl) mercury in refluxing benzene gives 10,10-dibromobicyclo (7.1.0) dec-1-ene (**45**) which reacts with methyl lithium to form cyclic cumulene, 1,2,3-cyclodecatriene (**46**), Scheme 21.

Scheme 21

(2) *Isomerization*²⁸⁻³⁰

Moore and Ward have been able to establish the cyclic allene (*1*)-acetylene (**47**) equilibrium using

potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol. The ratio of allene (*1*) to acetylene (**47**) at equilibrium is 13:2 indicating that the ring strain is more pronounced in acetylene than allene in a nine-membered system. This is not surprising since in an acetylene (**47**) four

carbon atoms are linear whereas in allene (*1*) only three are linear, Scheme 22.

Scheme 22

We have shown that (*1*) undergoes facile isomerization via *cis*, *cis*-1,3-cyclononadiene (*2*) and *cis*, *cis*-1,4-cyclononadiene (*4*) to *cis*, *cis*-1,5-cyclononadiene (*5*) by potassium *t*-butoxide in DMSO at 70° after 144 hr., Scheme 23. Thus, it would appear that *cis*, *cis*-1,5-cyclononadiene (*5*) is by a substantial margin, the most stable of the isomeric cyclononadienes.

Scheme 23

(3) Thermal Reactions³¹⁻³³

Dimerization of neat racemic 1,2-cyclononadiene (*1*) at 125° affords an essentially quantitative yield of a mixture of three isomers *48* (6%), *49* (63%) and *50* (31%). However, dimerization of optically active allene (*1*) gives *48* (0.4%), *49* (19.8%) and *50* (79.8%), Scheme 24. Clearly these results suggest that for the most part, dimerization stemming from the combination of *d*-allene with *d*-allene or *l*-allene with *l*-allene gives *50*, which is *meso*, while combination of *d*-allene with *l*-allene gives *48* and *49* which are not *meso*.

Scheme 24

bicyclo (4.3.0) non-7-ene (*52*) and *cis*-bicyclo (4.3.0) non-2-ene (*53*) in the ratio 65 : 23 : 12, Scheme 25. An attractive speculation is that thermal activation gives a vibrationally excited planar allene which can be viewed as two component radical units—a delocalized allylic system plus an orthogonal radical centre on the middle allenic carbon (*54*). Hydrogen transfer from an appropriate methylene group to one end of the allylic radical with subsequent or simultaneous bond reorganisation leads from the diradical species (*54*) to the acetylene (*51*) smoothly. The same intermediate can also be invoked to rationalize the formation of bicyclic products (*52* and *53*). Thus, transannular hydrogen abstraction by the central allenic carbon via five or six center process generates biradicals (*55* and *56*). Coupling of these species in the appropriate fashion gives the bicyclic olefins (*52* and *53*).

(4) Photochemical Reactions³⁴⁻³⁵

The benzene-sensitized photolysis of 1,2-cyclononadiene (*1*) in vapour phase at 2537 Å yields one major

product, tricyclic hydrocarbon (*58*), Scheme 26. The most reasonable pathway for the formation of tricyclic hydrocarbon is the closing of the allene to the cyclopropylidene (*57*) and subsequent transannular insertion of this species into the C-H bond. At very low conversions (0.1%), a plot of % conversion vs time gives a straight line, indicating that *58* is a primary product.

1,2-cyclononadiene (*1*) undergoes light induced 1,3- and 1,4-photochemical cycloaddition to benzene. Irradiation of 10% solution (v/v) of (*1*) in benzene gives principally 1 : 1 adducts in a 1 : 4 ratio. The

Scheme 25

Pyrolysis of 1,2-cyclononadiene (*1*) in a flow system at 640° and 0.3 mm pressure results in three products identified as 1-nonene-8-yne (*51*), *cis*-

major product has 1,4-structure (*59*), and the minor product (*60*) results from 1,3-cycloaddition, Scheme 27.

Scheme 26

Scheme 27

(5) Reduction³⁸⁻⁴⁰

The cyclic allene (1) undergoes stereospecific reduction to *cis*-cyclononene (11) by variety of procedures such as heterogeneous catalytic reduction or homogeneous catalytic reduction or metal-ammonia or hydroboration-protonolysis or diimide, Scheme 28.

Scheme 28

(6) Oxidation⁴¹⁻⁴²

Treatment of 1,2-cyclononadiene (1) with peracetic acid results in the formation of (7), (61), (62) and (63) (Scheme 29). The possible pathways for the formation of these products have been proposed *via* allene monoepoxide or allene diepoxide.

Scheme 29

(7) π -Complex Formation⁴³

Platinum (*o*) complex (64) of 1,2-cyclononadiene (1) has been prepared by generation of the allene in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine) (ethylene) platinum. Scheme 30.

Scheme 30

Reaction of 1,3-, 1,4- and 1,5-cyclonadiene (2,3,4 and 5)

(1) Thermal Reactions^{44,8}

Cis, trans-1,3-cyclononadiene (3) on heating to about 175 gives an equilibrium mixture of the diene (3) and the bicyclic olefin (65) in which the latter predominates. At temperature above 250° an irreversible isomerization of the bicyclic olefin (65) to *cis, cis*-1,3-cyclononadiene (2) takes place, Scheme 31. The observed stereospecificity of the cyclization is in accord with Woodward and Hoffman rule which predicts the observed conrotatory mode of cyclization of the diene (3) in its ground electronic state.

Scheme 31

Cis, cis-1,5-cyclononadiene (5) on heating to about 220° yields an equilibrium mixture containing 95% *cis, cis*-1,2-divinylcyclopentane (67) and 5% of the diene (5), Scheme 32. The formation of (67) indicates that the Cope rearrangement of (5) proceeds *via* a six-center transition state in which the carbon atoms of diallyl system are arranged in a boat form (66).

Scheme 32

(2) Photochemical Reactions⁴⁵

Irradiation of ether solution of *cis, trans*-1,3-cyclononadiene (3) with u.v. light of 300 nm gives rise to rapid isomerization to an approximate steady state in which the *cis, cis*-isomer (2) predominates. Slower process leads to the formation of a complex mixture containing two bicyclic olefins (68 and 69), 1,2-cyclononadiene (1), *cis, cis*-1,4-cyclononadiene (4), (52) and (53), Scheme 33. It has been proposed

that the *cis*-bicyclic olefin (69) results from a disrotatory cyclization arising from the excited state of *cis*, *cis*-isomer (2), and the *trans*-bicyclic olefin (68) arises similarly from the excited state of *cis*, *trans*-isomer (3). Such stereo selectivity is in accord with the

Scheme 33

postulated orbital symmetry rules for electrocyclic reactions by Woodward and Hoffman. In this respect *cis*, *trans*-1,3-cycloheptadiene (3) is the first example of a diene system in which the complementary modes of electrocyclization have been observed both in the electronic ground and excited states. The formation of other products is postulated to result from photochemically induced sigmatropic hydrogen shifts.

(3) Addition Reactions

(a) *Hydroboration*⁴⁶: Cyclic hydroboration-oxidation of *cis*, *cis*-1,5-cycloheptadiene (5) gives *cis*-1,4-

Scheme 34

(70) and *cis*-1,5-cycloheptanediol (71) in the ratio 1 : 4. However, isomerization of the intermediate organoboranes (74 and 75) at 70° for 4 hrs. followed by oxidation yields only (71), Scheme 34. This procedure provides a convenient stereospecific synthesis of *cis*-1,5-cycloheptanediol (71) for the first time.

The reaction involves the addition of BH_3 to one of the double bonds of (5) to form monocyclic organoboranes (72 and 73) which can undergo transannular addition to the other double bond to produce bicyclic organoboranes (74 and 75). Isomerization leads to conversion of 74 to 75 via elimination-addition to form the thermodynamically more stable bicyclic organoborane (75). We have also achieved similar transformations starting from either *cis*, *cis*-1,3-cycloheptadiene (2) or *cis*, *cis*-1,4-cycloheptadiene (4).

(b) *Transannular Additions*⁴⁷: We have shown that *cis*, *cis*-1,5-cycloheptadiene (5) is capable of undergoing stereospecific cyclization to *cis*-hexahydroindane derivatives via $C^+-\pi$ -interaction with electrophilic reagents like bromine, hydrogen bromide, mercuric acetate and lead tetraacetate. Bromination of (5) in CCl_4 gives the bicyclic dibromide (76) whereas in acetic acid it provides bromoacetate (77). The reaction with HBr gives a saturated bicyclic monobromo compound (78). Oxymercuration-demercuration according to Brown's procedure yields a bicyclic alcohol (79) as the sole product. Lead tetraacetate on the other hand provides a mixture of diacetate (80) and monoacetate (81) in which (80) is the major product, Scheme 35. It is interesting to note that the cyclization process is highly stereospecific in view of the many possibilities. The exact reason for such a stereocyclization process is not clear.

(4) π -Complex Formation⁴⁸⁻⁵¹

Dridding model construction of *cis*, *cis*-1,5-cycloheptadiene (5) shows that two important conformations, which have less steric interaction and more flexibility, are tub and chair like. Therefore, one would anticipate such a diene (5) to make π -complexes with transition metal ions in their low oxidation states

Scheme 35

such as Ag^+ , Cu^+ , Rh^+ , Pt^{+2} and Pd^{+2} . The complexes of all these transition metal ions with **(5)** have been made, and their physical properties have been examined. Based on their physical and spectral properties the possible structures have been proposed which are indicated in Scheme 36.

Scheme 36

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Very recently we have further shown that even 2 and 4 are capable of making π -complexes only with some transition metal ions.

Before I close my talk I wish to express my sincere gratitude to my students, Drs. G. C. Joshi, D. S. Sethi, G. Nagendrappa, R. Vaidyanathaswamy, Indu Mehrotra (Miss), and M. M. Bhagwat who are solely responsible for the execution of work described by me from our laboratory at I.I.T., Kanpur. Finally I thank you for your kind attention.

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